

SNUMBOOK AS HOME TASKS FOR AN ENHANCED NUMERACY LEVEL OF GRADE 7 STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the effectiveness of SNUMBOOK, a home task tool, for non-numerate Grade 7 students at Guinayang National High School in San Mateo Suboffice, Division of Rizal, for the SY 2023-2024. It addressed the identification of least mastered numeracy topics, evaluates SNUMBOOK's content, format, presentation, organization, and accuracy by parents, teachers, and experts, and analyzes the differences in these evaluations. The study also assessed student engagement—cognitive, behavioral, emotional, and social—before and after using SNUMBOOK, and measures the pretest and posttest performance of students. Methodologically, a descriptive and quasi-experimental one-group pretest-posttest design was employed, involving 60 evaluators and 30 students. Data were gathered using questionnaires and pretest-posttest assessments, analyzed using statistical methods such as mean percentage, Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test, Kruskal-Wallis Test, and Spearman's Rho. Results indicated significant improvement in numeracy and engagement levels post-intervention. SNUMBOOK was highly rated across all evaluative criteria with no significant differences among respondent groups. The engagement levels increased significantly, correlating positively with academic performance. Enhanced practice, support, and communication were identified as areas of improvement. The study concludes that SNUMBOOK effectively enhanced numeracy and engagement, suggesting its broader implementation and potential adaptation across various disciplines.

Keywords: *SNUMBOOK, numeracy, student engagement, educational tool, pretest-posttest, home tasks*

INTRODUCTION

This study focused on the development and validation of SNUMBOOK for Grade 7 students classified as non-numerate and emerging numerate based on competencies identified from the Numeracy Assessment Tool of DepEd Rizal. The primary objective was to enhance the numerical abilities and engagement levels of students at Guinayang National High School in San Mateo District, Rizal. Implemented during the second quarter of the school year 2023-2024, SNUMBOOK aimed to improve basic numeracy skills in Mathematics. To ensure its effectiveness, the material was evaluated by twenty parents, twenty Math teachers, and twenty experts from public schools in San Mateo, Rizal.

Participants in this study included thirty Grade 7 students identified as non-numerates and emerging numerates during the academic year 2023-2024. The study focused on basic mathematical skills, with the SNUMBOOK used as home tasks validated using Department of Education evaluation tools. Student performance was measured using pre-tests (without SNUMBOOK) and post-tests (after using SNUMBOOK) based on the Numeracy Assessment Tool. Additionally, the level of engagement of respondents was evaluated before and after using the developed material.

Many students transitioning from primary to secondary education have been found to be below their expected numeracy level, a concern highlighted by DepEd's introduction of its MATATAG agenda. The first 'Ma' in MATATAG stands for "make the curriculum relevant to produce competent and job-ready, active, and responsible citizens" (Department of Education, 2023). This foundational principle underscores the necessity of this study. Research such as that of Songsirisak (2019) suggests that homework can improve student learning but may reduce free time. Tucker (2020) concluded about how home-based activities have been shown to enhance pupils' grades and foster independent and responsible learning. Inspired by these findings, the researcher of this study developed SNUMBOOK to increase student engagement in Mathematics and improve numeracy. Unlike the KUMON method, which focuses on a home-based individualized learning program, SNUMBOOK was tailored to meet the needs of public-school students lacking grade-level mathematical competency.

There are several literatures that supports the efficacy of home-based activities in enhancing academic skills. Burke (2020) notes that these activities allow students to explore their comprehension at their own pace, fostering diverse learning methods. This aligns with the study by McCormick et al. (2020) among low-income families which concluded that home learning activities can significantly improve academic skills, a finding pertinent to this study since many participants come from low-income families with limited access to technology and private tutoring. Layug ((2021) increased the numeracy of grade 7 students through different interventions such as provision of added materials and remedial classes.

Pelayo (2023) found that remedial lessons and learning support tools helped Grade 9 pupils with non-numeracy. This supports the current study's use of SNUMBOOK

for additional learning. Belleza (2023) showed that global learning packets with family involvement improved non-numerate students' numeracy, emphasizing the relevance of parental engagement and innovative resources. An intriguing study by Munro et al. (2021) found that home numeracy exercises increase children's math skills. Nelson (2023) had the same findings with a conclusion that home math activities with parents improve math achievement by 84%. Luna (2023) established that the MATHSANAY Numeracy Projects greatly enhanced non-numerate pupils' skills. This suggests SNUMBOOK could close numeracy gaps as well.

The current study aimed to address the research gap in effective interventions for non-numerate Grade 7 students. By developing and validating SNUMBOOK, the researchers seek to provide a practical and impactful solution to enhance students' numerical abilities and engagement in Mathematics.

Research Questions

This research determined the effects of SNUMBOOK on the level of engagement and performance of the grade 7 students of Guinayang National High School, San Mateo District, Division of Rizal during the second quarter period for the school year 2023-2024.

Specifically, this research answered the following questions:

1. What were the least mastered topics measured in the Numeracy Assessment that were developed in the SNUMBOOK?
2. What was the evaluation of parents, Mathematics teachers, and experts on the developed SNUMBOOK as home task for grade 7 students in terms of?
 - a. Content;
 - b. Format;
 - c. Presentation and Organization; and
 - d. Accuracy and up-to-datedness of information?
3. Were there significant differences in the evaluation of the SNUMBOOK by the three groups of respondents based on the aforementioned criteria?
4. What was the level of engagement of the students before and after the use of SNUMBOOK in terms of:
 - a. Cognitive Engagement;
 - b. Behavioral Engagement;
 - c. Emotional Engagement;
 - d. Social Engagement?
5. Was there a significant difference in the level of engagement of the students before and after the use of SNUMBOOK?
6. What was the performance of the students during the pretest and posttest with SNUMBOOK?
7. Was there a significant difference between the mean scores of the pretest and posttest of the students?

8. Was there a significant relationship between the mean scores of the level of engagement and mean scores of the academic performance of the students after the use of SNUMBOOK?
9. What were the areas improved through SNUMBOOK with Parental Involvement at Homes?
10. What were the comments and suggestions of the teachers and students in using SNUMBOOK?

METHODOLOGY

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted at a public secondary school in the San Mateo District, Rizal, during the second quarter of the school year 2023-2024. The focus was on Grade 7 students identified as non-numerate and emerging numerate based on competencies from the Numeracy Assessment Tool of DepEd Rizal.

Sampling Method and Respondents

Purposive sampling was used to select the study participants. The respondents included:

- **Parents:** Twenty parents of Grade 7 students.
- **Math Teachers:** Twenty Math teachers from public schools in San Mateo District.
- **Math Experts:** Twenty experts in Mathematics education.
- **Students:** Thirty Grade 7 students identified as non-numerate and emerging numerate.

Demographics of Respondents

The student respondents were assessed using the Numeracy Assessment Tool to determine their numeracy levels. The parents, Math teachers, and experts were chosen based on their involvement with the participating students and their expertise in Mathematics education.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data collection process involved several steps:

1. **Permission and Consent:**
 - Permission was obtained from the Research and Development Office, the Superintendent of Rizal Schools Division, and the principals of participating schools.
 - Informed consent was secured from the parents of student respondents.
2. **Development of SNUMBOOK:**
 - Home tasks were developed based on feedback from the researcher's adviser, critics, and Math experts.

- The revised SNUMBOOK was validated by five secondary education experts and further refined.
- 3. Implementation:**
 - A pretest using the Numeracy Assessment Tool was administered to the students.
 - Students identified as non-numerate and emerging numerate were given the SNUMBOOK for home-based tasks.
 - After completing the SNUMBOOK exercises, a posttest and engagement survey were administered.
- 4. Evaluation:**
 - Questionnaires were distributed to parents, Math teachers, and experts to evaluate the SNUMBOOK.
 - Interviews were conducted with parents to assess their involvement and the areas improved through SNUMBOOK.

Instruments Used

- 1. Numeracy Assessment Tool (NUMAT):**
 - Utilized to measure students' numeracy levels as both pretest and posttest.
- 2. Questionnaire-Checklist for Parents, Mathematics Teachers, and Experts:**
 - Evaluated content, format, organization, and accuracy of SNUMBOOK using a four-point Likert scale (Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree).
- 3. Interview Questionnaire for Parents:**
 - Assessed areas improved through SNUMBOOK.
- 4. Math and Science Engagement Scales:**
 - Adapted from Ming Te Wang et al. (2016) to measure students' engagement levels before and after using SNUMBOOK.

Data Analysis

Statistical Treatments

- 1. Weighted Mean:**
 - Used to assess the input of teachers, experts, and parents on SNUMBOOK.
- 2. Mean Percentage Score:**
 - Calculated to determine the mastery level of students on specific topics.
- 3. Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test:**
 - Evaluated the significant difference between pretest and posttest scores, as well as engagement levels before and after using SNUMBOOK.
- 4. Kruskal-Wallis Test:**
 - Tested the significant difference among the evaluations of parents, Math teachers, and experts.
- 5. Spearman Rho:**
 - Examined the relationship between students' engagement levels and academic performance.

Score Range and Verbal Interpretation for the Pretest/Posttest

76-100	Above Numerate
51-75	Numerate
25-50	Emergent Numerate
00-25	Non-numerate

Scope and Limitations

This study focused on developing and validating SNUMBOOK for Grade 7 students classified as non-numerate and emerging numerate. The implementation was limited to the second quarter of the school year 2023-2024 and was evaluated by a specific group of parents, Math teachers, and experts from public schools in San Mateo, Rizal. The study did not cover other grade levels or students outside the identified numeracy levels.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

1. The least mastered topics measured in the Numeracy Assessment that were developed in the SNUMBOOK

Table 1: Mean Percentage Score and Mastery Level of Topics in the Numeracy

	TOPICS	MEAN PERCENTAGE SCORE	MASTERY LEVEL
ORAL TEST	Oral Counting	84.00	Near Full Mastery
	Rational Counting	75.40	Near Full Mastery
	Number Identification	89.40	Near Full Mastery
WRITTEN TEST	Number discrimination	60.00	Near Mastery
	Missing Number	65.40	Near Mastery
	Addition	54.70	Near Mastery
	Subtraction	46.70	Low Mastery
	Addition and Subtraction	49.30	Low Mastery
	Multiplication	30.70	Low Mastery
	Division	19.30	Low Mastery
	Multiplication and Division	15.00	Low Mastery
	Word Problems	4.00	Low Mastery
	Geometric Pattern	24.00	Low Mastery
	Geometric Visualization	6.00	Low Mastery

Table 2: Least Mastered Topics in Numeracy Assessment as the Basis for Developing the SNUMBOOK

Topics	
1	Number Discrimination
2	Missing Number
3	Addition

4	Subtraction
5	Multiplication
6	Division
7	Word Problems
8	Geometric Pattern and Visualization

As shown in Table 1, the results of the Numeracy Assessment for Grade 7 students show that the average score for topics covered in the written test is below 75%, indicating a level of near mastery and low mastery. The results indicate that the students found the topics covered in the written test as challenging. It identified specific areas where Grade 7 students should improve their abilities and acquire the needed skills. The least-mastered skills identified provided the basis for the topic necessary for students who had low numeracy levels in the development of the SNUMBOOK. On the other hand, Table 2 shows the least mastered topics identified using the Numeracy Assessment Tool provided by the Department of Education (DepEd) of Rizal. These topics present challenges that impede students' progress, resulting in difficulty in understanding previous concepts and limiting their ability to grasp new ones. The scores of the respondents reveal weaknesses in their numeracy skills for the written topics specified in Table 3. As a result, these topics have been included in the home tasks for the grade 7 students for the academic year 2023-2024 as part of the Mathematics Department's intervention program.

The topics covered address the essential numeracy abilities necessary for achieving numerical competency at the grade 7 level. The content begins with number discrimination and the identification of missing numbers, and then advances to fundamental mathematical operations. This is consistent with the findings of Padlan et al. (2023), who conducted research involving grade 10 participants. The investigation revealed that the average scores of the respondents in the areas of addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division were regarded as 'requiring improvement. SNUMBOOK progress further with the inclusion of word problems, geometric pattern, and visualization for the students to apply their skills in real-life scenarios and spatial reasoning.

2. The evaluation of parents, Mathematics teachers, experts, and parents on the developed SNUMBOOK in terms of content, format, presentation and organization, and accuracy and up-to-datedness of information.

Table 3. Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed SNUMBOOK in Terms of Content

Indicators	Respondents					
	Parents		Teachers		Master Teachers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Content is suitable to the student's level of development and has the potential to arouse the interest of the students.	3.85	SA	3.80	SA	3.85	SA

2. Material contributes to the achievement of specific objectives of the subject area.	3.75	SA	3.60	SA	3.70	SA
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3. Material enhances the development of desirable traits such as higher cognitive skills, critical thinking skills, creativity, learning by doing inquiry, problem-solving, etc.	3.70	SA	3.65	SA	3.70	SA
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Continuation of Table 3. Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed SNUMBOOK in Terms of Content

4. Materials are free of ideological, cultural, religious, racial, and gender biases and prejudices.	3.60	SA	3.70	SA	3.70	SA
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5. Adequate warning and cautionary notes are provided in the activities where safety and health are of concern.	3.85	SA	3.75	SA	3.80	SA
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Overall Weighted Mean	3.75	SA	3.70	SA	3.75	SA
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Standard Deviation	0.48		0.50		0.44	
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Legend: WM –Weighted Mean VI – Verbal Interpretation SA – Strongly Agree

It can be observed in Table 3 that parents, Math teachers, and experts have an evaluation with a verbal interpretation of **'Strongly Agree'** on the content of the SNUMBOOK. This confirms that the content of the developed SNUMBOOK is suitable to the student's level of development, contributes to the achievement of specific objectives, enhances the development of desirable traits, is free of ideological, cultural, religious, racial, and gender biases and prejudices and has adequate warning and cautionary notes.

Table 4. Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed SNUMBOOK in Terms of Format

Indicators	Respondents					
	Parents		Teachers		Master Teachers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Size and spaces of letters are appropriate to the intended users.	3.65	SA	3.55	SA	3.60	SA
2. Printing is good quality.	3.65	SA	3.85	SA	3.75	SA
3. Illustrations are easily recognizable, properly labeled, and supplement the text.	3.75	SA	3.80	SA	3.70	SA
4. Layout is simple and pleasing.	3.55	SA	3.95	SA	3.75	SA
5. Harmonious blending of illustrations and text.	3.55	SA	3.70	SA	3.70	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.63	SA	3.77	SA	3.70	SA
Standard Deviation	0.53		0.47		0.46	

Legend: WM –Weighted Mean VI – Verbal Interpretation SA – Strongly Agree

It can be seen in Table 4 that the parents, Math teachers, and experts evaluated ‘**Strongly Agree**’ on format of the developed SNUMBOOK. This shows that the format of the finished SNUMBOOK is appropriate, with the right font size, spacing, and illustrations. It also has simple and pleasing layout that is easy-to-understand and the illustrations and text have harmonious blending.

Table 5. Respondents’ Evaluations on the Developed SNUMBOOK in terms of Presentation and Organization

Indicators	Respondents					
	Parents		Teachers		Experts	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Presentation is engaging, interesting, and understandable	3.80	SA	3.80	SA	3.80	SA
2. There is a logical and smooth flow of ideas.	3.60	SA	3.70	SA	3.90	SA
3. Vocabulary level is adapted to the student’s likely experience and level of understanding.	3.70	SA	3.75	SA	3.70	SA
4. Sentences are suitable to the comprehension level of the students.	3.55	SA	3.70	SA	3.70	SA
5. Sentences and paragraph structure are varied and interesting to the students.	3.70	SA	3.70	SA	3.80	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.67	SA	3.73	SA	3.78	SA
Standard Deviation	0.47		0.47		0.42	

Table 5 with weighted means that are verbally interpreted as ‘Strongly Agree’ validates that presentation and organization of the developed SNUMBOOK is interesting, engaging, and easy to understand; the ideas are reasonable and flow well; the language is appropriate for the students’ level of understanding and experience; the sentences and paragraphs are well-structured and varied.

Table 6. Respondents’ Evaluations on the Developed SNUMBOOK in terms of Accuracy and Up-to-Datedness of the Information

Indicators	Respondents					
	Parents		Teachers		Master Teachers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Activity sheet has no conceptual errors.	3.90	SA	3.90	SA	3.95	SA
2. Activity sheet has no factual errors.	3.75	SA	3.85	SA	3.95	SA
3. Activity sheet has no grammatical errors.	3.85	SA	3.80	SA	3.85	SA
4. Activity sheet has no obsolete information.	3.75	SA	4.00	SA	3.90	SA
5. Activity sheet has no typographical and other minor errors (e.g., inappropriate unclear illustrations, missing labels, and wrong captions).	3.80	SA	3.75	SA	3.65	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.81	SA	3.86	SA	3.78	SA
Standard Deviation	0.42		0.35		0.40	

Legend: WM –Weighted Mean VI – Verbal Interpretation SA – Strongly Agree

Table 6, with weighted means that are verbally interpreted as ‘Strongly Agree’, validates that the content of the developed SNUMBOOK is suitable to its intended users. Precision of data is essential, particularly in the context of educational materials. Accurate and pertinent information improves understanding of the many concepts encompassed in the subject matter and enables more effective decision-making.

3. Test of differences in the evaluation of the SNUMBOOK by the three groups of respondents.

Table 7. Test of Difference in the Evaluation of the Three Groups of Respondents on the Developed SNUMBOOK

	Respondents						Kruskal -Wallis χ^2	P- value	Decision	VI
	Parents		Teachers		Experts					
	OW M	IV	OWM	IV	OWM	IV				
Content	3.75	SA	3.70	SA	3.75	SA	1.45	0.49	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Format	3.63	SA	3.77	SA	3.70	SA	0.50	0.78	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Presentation and Organization	3.67	SA	3.73	SA	3.78	SA	1.71	0.42	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Accuracy and up- to-datedness of the information	3.81	SA	3.86	SA	3.86	SA	0.06	0.97	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant

Legend: WM –Weighted Mean

VI – Verbal Interpretation

SA – Strongly Agree

As shown in Table 7, the evaluations of parents, Math teachers and expert respondents on the SNUMBOOK as home tasks content, format, presentation and organization, accuracy, and up-to-datedness of the information do not show significant difference. This means that the respondents’ evaluations are the same. Table 7 shows that in all categories, the respondents evaluated **strongly agreed** with the created SNUMBOOK, indicating that it meets the needs of students and is suitable. It can be concluded that the developed material shows an organized and systematic approach that corresponds to the Department of Education Curriculum requirements.

4. The level of engagement of the students before and after the use of SNUMBOOK in terms of Cognitive Engagement, Behavioral Engagement, Emotional Engagement, and Social Engagement

Table 8. Level of Mathematics Engagement of the Students Before and After the Use of SNUMBOOK as regards Cognitive Engagement

COGNITIVE ENGAGEMENT	Respondents			
	Before		After	
	OWM	VI	OWM	VI
1. I go through the work for math class and make sure that it's right.	1.80	ML	3.50	VHL
Continuation of Table 8. Level of Mathematics Engagement of the Students Before and After the Use of SNUMBOOK as regards Cognitive Engagement				
2. I think about different ways to solve a problem.	1.67	ML	3.37	HL
3. I try to connect what I am learning to things I have learned before.	1.83	ML	3.40	HL
4. I try to understand my mistakes when I get something wrong.	1.77	ML	3.63	VHL
5. I would have to do the work rather than be told the answer.	1.70	ML	3.63	VHL
6. I think that hard when I am doing work for class.	1.57	ML	3.40	HL
7. When work is hard, I study each parts carefully.	1.67	ML	3.40	HL
8. I consistently put in the effort required to meet the necessary standards.	1.43	LL	3.53	HL
Overall Weighted Mean	1.68	ML	3.48	HL
Standard Deviation	0.49		0.60	
Legend: OWM –Overall Weighted Mean VI – Verbal Interpretation LL-Low Level ML- Moderate Level HL- High Level VHL-Very High Level				

Table 8 illustrates the level of Mathematics engagement of students before and after the utilization of SNUMBOOK in terms of cognitive engagement. The overall weighted mean for cognitive engagement before using the SNUMBOOK was 1.68 with a verbal interpretation of '**moderate level**' with a standard deviation of 0.49. After the usage of SNUMBOOK, the overall weighted mean increased to 3.48 with standard deviation of 0.60 and yields a verbal interpretation of '**high level**'.

This result shows that students are more interested in working on math problems, thinking about different ways to solve them, making connections between what they are learning and real life, realizing their mistakes, doing the work instead of being told the answer, and working hard when they are working on classwork after the use of the developed SNUMBOOK.

Table 9. Level of Mathematics Engagement of The Students Before and After the Use of SNUMBOOK as regards to Behavioral Engagement

BEHAVIORAL ENGAGEMENT	Respondents			
	Before		After	
	OWM	VI	OWM	VI
1. I stay focused.	1.67	ML	3.67	VHL
2. I put effort into learning math.	1.80	ML	3.60	VHL
3. I keep trying even if something is hard.	1.87	ML	3.60	VHL
4. I complete my homework on time.	1.40	LL	3.20	HL
5. I talk about math outside of class.	1.57	ML	3.27	HL
6. I participate in class.	1.63	ML	3.30	HL
Continuation of Table 9. Level of Mathematics Engagement of The Students Before and After the Use of SNUMBOOK as regards to Behavioral Engagement				
7. I give my full attention in class and avoiding things.	1.47	LL	3.67	VHL
8. I seek the help of my teacher if I don't understand.	1.73	ML	3.57	VHL
Overall Weighted Mean	1.64	ML	3.49	HL
Standard Deviation	0.57		0.66	

Legend: OWM –Overall Weighted Mean VI – Verbal Interpretation LL-Low Level
 ML- Moderate Level HL- High Level VHL-Very High Level

The level of mathematics engagement of students before and after the use of SNUMBOOK in terms of behavioral engagement is presented in Table 15 indicating a **'moderate level'** of engagement with overall weighted mean at 1.64 with standard deviation of 0.57 before the implementation of SNUMBOOK. the overall weighted mean increased to 3.49 with standard deviation of 0.66 and is interpreted as **'high level'**.

The rise in the results shows that the use of SNUMBOOK has improved students' focus and effort in math class, encouraged them to try new things even when they're difficult, pushed them to turn in their homework on time, increased their level of engagement outside of class, and encouraged them to ask their teacher for clarification when needed.

Table 10. Level of Mathematics Engagement of the Students Before and After the Use of SNUMBOOK as regards Emotional Engagement

EMOTIONAL ENGAGEMENT	Respondents			
	Before		After	
	OWM	VI	OWM	VI
1. I look forward to math class.	1.50	ML	3.67	VHL
2. I enjoy learning new things about math.	1.90	ML	3.73	VHL
3. I want to understand what is learned in math class.	1.83	ML	3.67	VHL

4. I feel good when I am in math class.	1.50	ML	3.70	VHL
5. I often feel happy in math class	1.97	ML	3.63	VHL
6. I think that math class is interesting.	1.70	ML	3.67	VHL
7. I want to be in math class.	1.30	LL	3.67	VHL
8. I care about learning math.	1.93	ML	3.70	VHL
9. I often feel excited when I am in math class.	1.43	LL	3.53	VHL
Overall Weighted Mean	1.67	ML	3.66	VHL
Standard Deviation	0.78		0.57	

It can be seen from Table 10 the level of mathematics engagement of the students before and after the implementation of SNUMBOOK in terms of emotional engagement. The overall weighted mean of the students pre-SNUMBOOK was at 1.67 with a verbal interpretation of 'moderate level'. After the use of the developed material, the overall weighted mean increased to 3.66 and verbally interpreted as 'very high level'. The findings indicate that the utilization of SNUMBOOK leads to increase of emotional engagement among students. The students now await math class with enthusiasm, get enjoyment from acquiring new mathematical concepts, and feel pleasure when engaging in arithmetic activities.

Table 11. Level of Mathematics Engagement of the Students Before and After the Use of SNUMBOOK as regards Social Engagement

SOCIAL ENGAGEMENT	Respondents			
	Before		After	
	OWM	VI	OWM	VI
1. I get confident when I learn new things about math.	1.80	ML	3.70	VHL
2. I build on others' ideas.	1.43	LL	3.40	HL
3. I try to understand other people's ideas in math class.	1.73	ML	3.50	VHL
4. I try to work with others who can help me in math.	1.70	ML	3.53	VHL
5. I try to help others who are struggling in Math	1.47	LL	3.33	HL
6. I care about other people's ideas	1.67	ML	3.53	VHL
7. When working with others, I share ideas	1.50	ML	3.23	HL
Overall Weighted Mean	1.61	ML	3.46	HL
Standard Deviation	0.53		0.65	

Prior to using SNUMBOOK, Table 11 reveals that the overall weighted mean was 1.61 with a standard deviation of 0.53 and a "moderate level" of verbal interpretation. With a verbal interpretation of "high level," the students' overall weighted mean improved to 3.46 with a standard deviation of 0.65 after the use of SNUMBOOK. The increase in results indicates that students are engaging in more social interactions after the use of SNUMBOOK. During group math activities, students actively participate by sharing their own ideas, actively expanding on the ideas of others, collaborating with classmates, and demonstrating enhanced confidence.

- The significant difference in the level of engagement of the students before and after the use of SNUMBOOK

Table 12. Summary of Test of Difference in the Level of Math Engagement of the Students Before and After the Use of SNUMBOOK

	Before		After		z-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD				
Cognitive	1.68	0.20	3.49	0.38	4.79	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Behavioral	1.66	0.29	3.49	0.50	4.79	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Emotional	1.70	0.30	3.65	0.43	4.79	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Social	1.61	0.30	3.46	0.44	4.79	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant

Presented in Table 12 the summary of the test of difference in the level of engagement before and after the use of the developed SNUMBOOK. The unanimous computed p- value of 0.000 across all areas is less than the level of significance at 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected statistically. This implies that the difference between the level of engagement before and after is significant.

There is evidence to suggest that the developed SNUMBOOK enhances level of cognitive, behavioral, emotional, and social engagement of students in math and promotes an enriched math learning experience.

- The performance of the students during the pretest and posttest with SNUMBOOK.

Table 13. Performance of the Respondents During the Pretest and Posttest in the Numeracy Assessment

Score	Descriptor	RESPONDENTS			
		Pretest		Posttest	
		f	%	f	%
76 - 100	Above Numerate	0	0.0	17	56.67
51 - 75	Numerate	0	0.0	12	40.00
26 - 50	Emerging Numerate	28	93.33	1	3.33
0 - 25	Non-numerate	2	6.67	0	0
Total		30	100.0	30	100.0
Mean		41.77		74.40	
Standard Deviation		7.46		12.54	
Descriptor		Emerging Numerate		Numerate	

Note: f- frequency

Table 13 presents the distribution of students' scores during the pretest and posttest in learning basic math skills using the SNUMBOOK as home tasks.

As seen the Table 13, the pretest results show that 28 out of 30 students, or 93.33%, received scores ranging from 26 to 50, placing them in the emerging numerate level, while 2 out of 30 students, or 6.76%, received scores ranging from 0 to 25, placing them in the non-numerate level.

After being immersed to the developed SNUMBOOK, 17 out of 30 or 56.67% of the students fall under **Above Numerate Level**. There are 12 out of 30 or 40.00% of the students fall under **Numerate Level**. The number of participants fall under **Emergent Numerate Level** was reduced to 1 out or 30 or 3.33%, and none of the students of the students fall under **Non-numerate Level** in the posttest. Furthermore, the pretest performance of the students has a mean score of 41.77 and a standard deviation of 7.46, interpreted as **Emerging Numerate**. The posttest performance of the students has a mean score increased to 74.40 and a standard deviation of 12.54 with verbal interpretation of **Numerate**. It can be concluded that academic performance and the level of numeracy among students have increase.

The current study yielded the same result as the study of Belleza (2023) about the increase of the post-test scores of the students after utilizing learning packets at home with parental involvement. Just like this study, Belleza (2023) invited parents to be hands-on and take charge of the numeracy skills of their children when they do home-based activities. This result means that the developed SNUMBOOK enhanced the level of numeracy and academic performance of the students.

7. The significant difference between the mean scores of the pretest and posttest of the students.

Table 14. Test of Difference Between the Mean Scores of the Pretest and Posttest

Tests	Mean Score	SD	z-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Pretest	41.77	7.49	4.78	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Posttest	74.40	12.19				

Note: $\alpha = 5\%$

As apparent from Table 14, the computed p- value of 0.000 is less than the level of significance of 0.05 resulting in the statistical decision to reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, there is sufficient evidence to support that there is a significant difference between the mean scores of the pretest and the posttest of the respondents There is proof to suggest that the students' numeracy level and academic performance increased after completing the SNUMBOOK.

The finding proves that SNUMBOOK is a beneficial tool for both teachers and students, successfully enhancing their mastery of numerical abilities, promoting academic progress, and enhancing numeracy level when utilized as tasks to be completed at home with the help of parents.

8. The relationship between the mean scores of the level of engagement and mean scores of the academic performance of the students after the use of SNUMBOOK

Summarized in Table 15, Spearman Rho coefficients (0.41, 0.57, 0.56, 0.47) reflecting the correlation between the level of engagement and academic performance of the students reveals a moderate positive correlation. With computed p-values (0.023, 0.000, 0.000, 0.009) less than the level of significance at 0.05, the statistical decision is to reject the null hypothesis. This shows a significant relationship between all aspects the level of engagement and academic performance after the utilization of SNUMBOOK.

Table 15. Test Relationship Between the Level of Engagement and the Academic Performance of the Students After the Use of SNUMBOOK

	Spearman-Rho Value	Strength	P-value	Decision	Interpretation
Cognitive Engagement Academic Performance	0.41	Moderate	0.023	Reject Ho	Significant
Behavioral Engagement Academic Performance	0.57	Moderate	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Emotional Engagement Academic Performance	0.56	Moderate	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Social Engagement Academic Performance	0.47	Moderate	0.009	Reject Ho	Significant

There is confirmation to suggest that as the level of cognitive, behavioral, emotional, and social engagement of students in math improves the students' academic performance also improves.

This confirms the SNUMBOOK could enhance the level of engagement and academic achievement of the students.

9. The areas improved through SNUMBOOK with Parental Involvement at Homes

The following are the answers of parents in the interview as regards to the areas improved through the SNUMBOOK.

- a. **Increased Practice and Reinforcement.** The answers of the parents that shows increased in practice and reinforcement as shown below:

Dahil ang SNUMBOOK ay mayroong mga practice exercises na nakabatay sa mga basic na kakayahang sa Math. Nagkaroon ang aking anak ng mga pagkakataong mag-enjoy at mag-apply ng kaniyang natutunan sa ibot-ibong uri ng mga problema. Ang araw araw na pag-aranay ay nakakotulong sa kanya na mapalakat ang kanyang kasanayan at kumpiyansa sa Math.

SA PAMATAGITAN NG PAGGAMIT NG SNUMBOOK, NAKATULONG ITO UPANG
HINDI LAHANG NAGING ABALA ANG AKING ANAK SA PAG-AARAL, NGUNIT NAGKARON
DIN SIYA NG MAHUSAY NA PAGKATAON NA MAPALAWAK ANG KANYANG
KALAMAHAN SA MGA ARALIN NA NAKIHIRAPAN SA SIYA.

As seen in the answers the SNUMBOOK provided the students with additional practice materials that reinforced the development of their numerical skills. The parents noted that they appreciated how the materials kept their children busy while they were at home. They also appreciated the chance for their children to practice mathematics at home.

- b. **Support and Encouragement.** The answers of the parents on the improved support and encouragement were presented below.

mas lalo akong nagiging aktibo sa pag suport sa aking anak gamit ang SNUMBOOK dahil alam ko na nakikipapan-apa sa math. sinuportahan ko at ginagabay ko ang aking anak dahil alam kong ito ay magpapalakat ng kanyang kumpiyansa at pagmamahal sa pag-aaral na magbubunga ng mas matagumpay at mas makabuluhan na pag-unlad sa kanyang buhay.

ANG PAGGAMIT NG SNUMBOOK AY NAGBIHAY SA AMING MAG-INA
 NG MAS MARAMING PAGKATAON NA MAGKARON NG UGNA-
 YAN AT PAGTUTULUNGAN BILANG MAGULANG AT ANAK. ITO NAG
 BIBIGAY DAAN SA MAS MALALIM NA SAMAHAN SA AMIN
 DAHIL SA BINIBAY KONTO PAGESUPORTA SA AKING ANAK.
 NAGKARON NA NG KALAMAHAN ANG AKING ANAK SA
 MATEMATIKA DAHIL SA SNUMBOOK, IPINALIWANAG NYA
 MABUTI ANG BAWAT TANONG AT KUNING PAPANONG SOLVE
 ANG MGA NUMERO. MARAMING SALAMAT PO...

As gleaned in the answers the material improves the support and encouragement of the parents and the teachers. The students learned to ask questions from the teachers to understand their SNUMBOOK activities further. At home, the parents noted that they were often asked by their children to explain the tasks and guide them in accomplishing their tasks. Several parents shared how they fully supported their children and encouraged them to finish all tasks no matter how challenging the tasks were.

c. **Communication.** The answers of the parents on the improved communication were stated below:

NAGKARON NG PAGKATAON AT MAKITA AT MALAMAN
 ANG KALAGAYAN NG AKING ANAK SA PAMAMAGITAN
 NG PAGPILIHA NG (SNUMBOOK) PERFORMANCE REPORT SA
 TUNILLO MATATAPOS ANG GAWIN NGA SA SNUMBOOK ITO
 AY NAGBIBIGAY SA AKING NG PAGKATAON UPANG
 MAHONITOR ANG KANYANG TALA ABILIDAD AT TROUMPIYU
 SA PAGPILIHA NA TATAPINU MAGIHU INSPIRASYUN
 UPANG LALUNU MAGPARTISIPARON ANG AKING ANAK

Ang paggamit ng SNUMBOOK ay nakakatulong sa akong anak
 na maunawaan ang kanyang mga pagkakamali dahil ito sa Mabilis
 na pagmamagitan ng gawa at magkakaroon ng pagkakatayang
 Humid ang mga ito bago pa sila magpatuloy sa
 kanilang pag-aaral. Ito ay ipinalam sa akin ng
 kanyang guro sa pamamagitan ng pagpirmang ng mga
 marka ng kanyang gawain

The teachers were able to clearly show to the parents about the mathematical skills of their children through the SNUMBOOK. The parents were able to share to the teachers as well about exactly which part of the SNUMBOOK their children are still hard up with. Generally, the implementation of the SNUMBOOK opened a communication between the parents and the teachers as they partnered up to help the students improve their mathematical skills.

This suggests that structured parental involvement in facilitating the SNUMBOOK has cumulative effects, resulting improvement in numeracy skills among learners with low numeracy level, allowing them to continue learning basic numeracy at home.

10. The comments and suggestions of the teachers and students in using SNUMBOOK.

The comments given by parents, mathematics educators, and experts on the utilization of SNUMBOOK to enhance the developed home tasks for Grade 7 are as follows:

The material was well thought of and could really help students. (b) The SNUMBOOK, will help the students to develop their skills and interest in learning the concept in Mathematics. (c) The SNUMBOOK is great and very engaging because of the creativity on how it is made. (d) The contents are amazing and appropriate to the level of the learner. (e) The presentation of the SNUMBOOK is engaging and the skills are applicable to slow and average students. It is highly recommended. (f) Suitable for non-numerates/ remedial students. (g) The materials are good activity supplement for the non-numeric students, and it is innovative that may catch the interest of the students. (h) The module is interactive and interesting. (i) It is well organized and easy to understand. (j) Congratulations! It was a good and entertaining SNUMBOOK. I hope that our future learners will utilize your skill numeracy booklets. (j) Your skill numeracy booklet was entertaining.

The student will surely love to answer this booklet. (k) The material has clear illustration and consistently formatted. This will help avoid confusion and make it for students to follow along. (l) Students will be able to study and appreciate mathematics at their own pace with the aid of this SNUMBOOK, with SuperNumboy's help the topics are presented in an interesting and understandable manner. (m) Excellent! Big help for students struggling in Math especially those who are non-numerate. (n) I am sure and confident that the developed material will greatly help the students to master their skills in mathematics and will encourage them to learn mathematics. Well done! Congratulations! (o) The SNUMBOOK, is appropriate for their developmental stage and can spark curiosity. (p) The arrangement is lovely rather than appealing. Overall, it's excellent.

The following **suggestions** were offered by the respondents on SNUMBOOK as home task for Grade 7 students with low numeracy level.

“I suggest adding some items that are more challenging or with hot questions.” (b) Make the font size uniformed. (c) Use simple words and instructions. (d) Usage of bi-lingual instruction could be used for student to better comprehend the SNUMBOOK. (e) Avoid using dark and bright colors for illustrations on activities to give highlights in the text balloons. (f) If possible, consider incorporating interactive elements, such as foldout diagrams and pop-ups. (g) Don't overcrowd the page with too much information. (Use simple terminologies. (h) If possible, definition of terms or glossary maybe added for fully understanding of concepts especially the difference between subtraction and addition with and without regrouping. (i) I suggest you add more exercises for each skill to improve mastery. (j) Create an example box for each skill.

The SNUMBOOK can aid student in learning math, according to the respondents. It is entertaining due to its distinctive style and student-friendly information. The content is highly recommended because it engages both average and slow learners. Students that are remedial or non-numerate can benefit from SNUMBOOK. Students who don't like numbers will be interested in these imaginative activity additions. The curriculum required parents' direction in addition to the students' full engagement. It's easy to understand, interesting, and well-organized. However, they recommended include a few more difficult topics or questions with HOTS. Consistency in font sizes helps to simplify words and directions. Home tasks in two languages could aid in SNUMBOOK comprehension. It is not appropriate to use bright or dark colors while drawing text balloon highlights. It is advised to use foldout diagrams and pop-ups as interactive elements. Don't fill the entire page. Definitions or glossaries let students add and subtract without having to regroup.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The evaluations of parents, Math teachers and experts on the developed SNUMBOOK do not differ significantly as to Content, Format, Presentation and Organization, and Accuracy and up-to datedness of the information. SNUMBOOK meets students' needs and is well-suited, organized, and methodical, aligning with the curriculum criteria set by the Department of Education.
2. The developed SNUMBOOK enhances the level of numeracy and is effective material to improve learning, as evidenced by the increase in the post test. As a result, the numeracy level of student is enhanced.
3. The cognitive, behavioral, emotional, and social engagement of students is improved after the usage of the developed the usage of SNUMBOOK. Thus, it promotes an enriched math learning experience.
4. There is a significant relationship exists between the level of engagement and the of the academic performance of the students after the use of SNUMBOOK. Therefore, this proves that if the level of engagement improves, the level of academic performance of the students also improves. Thus, students must be engaged to improve mastery and proficiency in Mathematics.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn, the following are recommended:

1. Students who struggle with numeracy may utilize the SNUMBOOK due to its ability to accommodate individual learning speeds and enhance their numerical proficiency even at home.
 2. Teachers may engage in collaborative efforts to apply the discoveries of the study towards the improvement and enhancing of home tasks.
 3. School administrators may continue to provide their support, make any required modifications, and guarantee the full implementation of assigning home tasks, as it helps pupils improve their numeracy skills and actively participate in mathematics.
 4. Other educational institutions in the district may utilize this resource as it has the capacity to assist the students to reach their desired level of numeracy and enhances mathematics engagement both within the classroom environment and at home.
 5. Future researchers may carry out a comparative study in different academic disciplines and adapt or improve the content based on the students' requirements.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study followed the ethical guidelines for conducting research with the student respondents. Before commencing the data collection process, the researcher made certain that informed consent was acquired from the parents and the student participants. The participants were provided with information regarding the study's objective, the utilization of the data, and the voluntary aspect of their involvement. In addition, the participants' information was ensured to be confidential, and any identifiable data was eliminated during the data processing phase to safeguard their privacy.

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